

On metric of homogenous gravitational field

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Abstract

The Christoffel’s criterion of his symbols independence on coordinates in a homogenous field offers a metric of a homogenous field of accelerations. However, this result is ambiguous. So the issue of a metric existence of a homogenous gravitational field remains open. Thus, the task of finding the only physically justified metric of a homogeneous gravitational field is posed and possible solutions to this problem are proposed.

Keywords: Accelerated motion, Gravitational field, Homogenous field, Christoffel symbols.

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1. Introduction

Any continuous field within limits of its small areas is homogenous. That is why any theory must contain a description of a homogenous field. Unfortunately, in the general relativity theory, a homogenous field metric is unknown.

Usually, a homogenous field description doesn't cause any trouble. It is just enough to keep in mind that a scalar or a vector of this field must not depend on coordinates. Nevertheless any gravitational field is described by a metric and finding of this field metric poses many serious problems.

In 1907, A. Einstein [1] developed his equivalence principle for a homogenous field of acceleration. With aid of this principle, Einstein solved the clock rate problem in a homogenous gravitational field. Based on the principle of the light speed invariability and the symmetry considerations, Einstein came to the following exact ratio in the homogenous gravitational field:

$$d\tau = \exp\left(\frac{gx}{c^2}\right) dt, \quad (1)$$

where $\varphi = -gx$ is potential of gravitational field.

Seemingly, the subsequent development of the relativistic theory of the gravitation should confirm the formula (1), since within limits of a small area, any continuous field is homogenous. However, this did not happen².

The Einstein's solution of the equation provides us with nothing more than approximations. For example, the homogenous field linear approximation found by V. A. Fock [2] can be considered to be the first approximation of the homogenous field.

$$ds^2 = \left(1 + \frac{2gx}{c^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2gx}{c^2}\right) \cdot (dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2), \quad (2)$$

Note that the expression (2) is not a solution of the Einstein equation.

Only in 1963, Harry Lass [3] described the homogenous unidimensional accelerated system. Based on the first principles and the invariance of the light speed, H. Lass deducts the non-

isomorphic transformation of an inertial reference system to a non-inertial (homogeneous) one:

$$ds^2 = c^2 t^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 = e^{\frac{2gX}{c^2}} (c^2 T^2 - dX^2) - dY^2 - dZ^2 \quad (3)$$

This metric belongs to the flat space. Let's pay attention that the parameter g_{00} of this metric coincides with the coefficient in the Einstein's formula (1). However, the metric (2) is anisotropic and is not the only metric with this motion law in the direction X .

Figure 1. Changing of local spatial and temporal scales at changes of a parameter, which depends on coordinates.

Source: Author.

2. Proofmass in homogenous gravitational field

The main sign of the homogenous gravitational field is the vector invariability of the free fall acceleration:

$$\mathbf{g} = \text{const}. \quad (4)$$

The free fall acceleration of a "fixed" point in the ordinary coordinates is equal to

$$g_x = \frac{d^2 X}{dT^2} = c^2 \Gamma_{00}^1. \quad (5)$$

However, this equation gives no unambiguous solution. Besides, the invariability of this parameter does not answer the question, whether such metric is truly homogenous or not. The equation (5) is true only for stationary proofmasses. In the general case, it is necessary to take the speed into account because the motion equation in the general relativity theory contains the following speeds:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{ds^2} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\mu \frac{dx^\alpha}{ds} \frac{dx^\beta}{ds} = 0.$$

² It is possible to imagine an absolutely other course of development of the theory, if Schwarzschild would use the expression (1) as a condition on infinity.

Following [4], it is correct to write the following equation for the ordinary time:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{dt^2} = -\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\mu \frac{dx^\alpha}{dt} \frac{dx^\beta}{dt} + \frac{1}{c} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^0 \frac{dx^\alpha}{dt} \frac{dx^\beta}{dt} \frac{dx^\mu}{dt} \quad (6)$$

or

$$\frac{d^2 x^i}{dt^2} = -c^2 \Gamma_{00}^i - 2c \Gamma_{0k}^i \frac{dx^k}{dt} - \Gamma_{mn}^i \frac{dx^m}{dt} \frac{dx^n}{dt} + \left\{ c \Gamma_{00}^0 + 2 \Gamma_{0k}^0 \frac{dx^k}{dt} + \frac{1}{c} \Gamma_{mn}^0 \frac{dx^m}{dt} \frac{dx^n}{dt} \right\} \frac{dx^i}{dt}. \quad (6a)$$

Thus, the proofmasses' behavior identity in any homogenous field is ensured in virtue of the following condition:

$$\Gamma_{mn}^i = \text{const}, \text{ and } \Gamma_{mn}^0 = \text{const}. \quad (7)$$

Indeed, for Lass metric (3), the non-zero Christoffel symbols comply with the equalities

$$\Gamma_{11}^1 = \Gamma_{00}^1 = \Gamma_{10}^0 = \Gamma_{01}^0 = \frac{g}{c^2}.$$

Now we see that for sure, the metric (3) is homogenous. Is this metric corresponds to a gravitational field, too? After all, it is strange that it belongs to flat 4D-space and even stranger is the fact that this metric is anisotropic in the ordinary space.

3. Metric of homogenous isotropic gravitational field

In a homogenous gravitational field with an acceleration in the direction x , the coordinates y and z are tantamount. That is why in the general form, the metric of the homogenous gravitational field can be written down like this:

$$\Gamma_{11}^1 = -\Gamma_{22}^1 = -\Gamma_{33}^1 = \Gamma_{00}^1 = \Gamma_{12}^2 = \Gamma_{21}^2 = \Gamma_{13}^3 = \Gamma_{31}^3 = \Gamma_{10}^0 = \Gamma_{01}^0 = \frac{g}{c^2}.$$

The metric (9) is not only homogenous but it is isotropic as well. In addition, this metric has the non-zero Riemannian curvature and its convolutions. For example, the scalar curvature is equal to

$$R = \frac{6g^2 e^{-\frac{2gx}{c^2}}}{c^4}.$$

$$ds^2 = s(x)c^2 t^2 - p(x)dx^2 - q(x)d(y^2 - dz^2).$$

Let us calculate the non-zero Christoffel symbols:

$$\Gamma_{11}^1 = \frac{p'}{2p};$$

$$\Gamma_{22}^1 = \Gamma_{33}^1 = \frac{-q'}{2p};$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^1 = \frac{s'}{2p}; \quad (8)$$

$$\Gamma_{12}^2 = \Gamma_{21}^2 = \Gamma_{13}^3 = \Gamma_{31}^3 = \frac{p'}{2p};$$

$$\Gamma_{10}^0 = \Gamma_{01}^0 = \frac{s'}{2s}.$$

The condition (7) is met by the functions s , p and q , if they are constants or take the form of e^{kx} , where k is a constant. This brings us to the following metric:

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2gx}{c^2}} (c^2 t^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2) \quad (9)$$

with the following Christoffel symbols:

The metric (9) belongs to the category of the conformally flat metrics. Upon that, a locally flat space gets mapped isomorphically to another locally flat space without rotations (see Fig. 1).

So a homogenous field of inertia can have a lot of different metrics. The criterion of the motion equation independence on coordinates does not provide a solution uniqueness of the expressions [5] and [6]. We do not know, whether – among possible solutions – the metric exists or not, which

is equivalent to the homogenous gravitational field.

4. Metric of homogeneous isotropic space without fields

Einstein and Fokker [7] noticed that a reference system with a constant (local) speed of light is described by the metric of the following form:

$$ds^2 = v^2(c^2 t^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2), \quad (10)$$

notably, v is a function of the coordinates. The space with the metric (1) can be referred to as conformal-Galilean.

The Christoffel symbols of this metric [8]

$$\Gamma_{10}^1 = \Gamma_{01}^1 = \Gamma_{20}^2 = \Gamma_{02}^2 = \Gamma_{03}^3 = \Gamma_{30}^3 = c^2 \Gamma_{11}^0 = c^2 \Gamma_{22}^0 = c^2 \Gamma_{33}^0 = \Gamma_{00}^0 = H_0$$

allow to assign this metric to a homogeneous empty space without fields or substance.

Such metric can serve as a fundament for construction of models of the Universe. The metric describes the Hubble law

$$z = \exp(H_0 T) - 1 \approx H_0 T.$$

5. Conclusion

The covariant divergence of the Einstein tensor is zero. That is why following Einstein, one may suggest that this tensor is proportional to the energy-momentum tensor. The proportionality coefficient between these values is known from the asymptotic behavior of these tensors in the Newtonian approximation³. These considerations allow to calculate the energy-momentum tensor

$$t_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \left(R_{ik} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ik} R \right) = \begin{pmatrix} 3p & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -p \end{pmatrix},$$

Let's give consideration to a space with the zero acceleration of proofmasses. The uniformity of the space-time continuum is provided by the condition specific for the non-zero Christoffel symbols (7). This condition transforms the metric (10) to the metric of the following form:

$$ds^2 = \exp(2H_0 T) (c^2 t^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2), \quad (11)$$

notably, H_0 is the only constant with a proper dimensionality and this is the Hubble constant.

where, $p = \frac{c^2 H_0^2}{8\pi G}$. The expression (4) does not depend on coordinates and thus, indeed, the metric (2) describes the homogeneous space-time continuum having a constant density and a negative pressure at every point of the space.

The metric (2) has the negative scalar curvature

$$R = -6 k_0^2 \exp(-2k_0 x).$$

Surprisingly, the density of the space of the homogeneous metric $\rho = 3p/c^2$ coincides perfectly with the Friedman critical density [9]

$$\rho = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}.$$

This confirms the ideas by A. A. Friedman.

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